

Design Factors for Atomic Clocks for Space

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Abstract - There are very strong differences between the designs of clocks for space applications and those used on earth. This paper discusses the performance impacts from differences in mechanical design, thermal design, radiation hardness, and control. The design changes necessary to survive launch and operate in space go beyond the expected issues of mechanical strength and remote control. There are a number of design trade-offs that can affect clock performance. For example, the added structural members needed to secure a microwave cavity may result in poor thermal control due to heat loss along the structure or de-tuning due to new stresses on the cavity structure. Reliability and radiation hardening drive performance less directly by limiting the availability of critical electronic component types. On the positive side, the lack of gravity, fluctuations in air temperature, and mechanical perturbations sometimes lead to space clocks running better than similar ground units. The differences between clocks for short-term space experiments and production space vehicles will be examined.

Keywords - Space, Atomic Clocks, Design

I. INTRODUCTION

The use of atomic clocks in space began in 1974 with the Navigation Technology Satellite I (NTS-1). NTS-1 was a technology development vehicle for the newly formed Global Positioning System (GPS). Those first two rubidium clocks were commercial clocks modified to withstand launch, be remotely controlled, and monitored via the spacecraft telemetry [1]. Since then GPS has flown dozens of cesium and rubidium clocks. These production clocks are quite different. The NTS-1 clocks were a space experiment, designed to show that it was possible use the technology on a satellite. They worked and laid the groundwork for the excellent GPS clocks that followed. However, they would be totally unacceptable in a current, production satellite.

II. CLASSES OF SPACE CLOCKS

There are two general classes of space clocks for applications in space. The first are space experiments, such as the NTS-1 rubidiums. The second are production clocks, such as the Perkin-Elmer rubidiums now operating in the GPS Block IIR satellites. The differences between the two classes of clocks are very significant. A clock designed for use in an operational satellite is one component of a complex system designed for a specific mission (Fig. 1). The design criteria is focused on satisfactory and reliable performance over the overall mission life [2]. The design life will typically be eight years or more. It must survive launch, radiation, and other space hazards and meet its full performance specification. In the other case, the clock designed for a space experiment would have a limited

mission. The purpose could be either to investigate its successful operation in space, or use in conjunction with another experiment for a different purpose, such as a sensor examining some space related phenomena. Design life for a space experiment is typically one to two years and is instrumented for a detailed investigation of operating parameters or related operation with another subsystem. The challenge for such experiments is for the clock to produce a given stability or accuracy in space. For operational use with a production clock, the challenge is reliable operation, a long life and predictable performance. A production design that meets operational system use is achieved as a result of a deliberate sequential development process. The factors that make a production design capable of operational use in space applications need to be designed in, not added on later.

III. DESIGN ISSUES

The key design issues for space atomic clocks for operational system use after stable and accurate performance are:

- 1) *Size and weight*: New clocks usually start as laboratory devices. The issue may be getting it work at all or to work well. Just about everything else is secondary until the performance goals seem achievable. For satellite use, these are essential factors from the start.
- 2) *Power*: Like size and weight, power is usually a secondary consideration here on earth. The driver for low power is usually battery size for portable operation or power outages. Power is an expensive commodity on a satellite.

3) *Ruggedness*: Surviving launch is the critical mechanical issue for any space clock. Random vibration levels for design qualification can be as high as 20 g's rms. Space Shuttle launched mission are typically lower but still well above normal for laboratory applications. The need for mechanical strength has dictated major design changes in clocks. A good example, the hydrogen maser will be examined in detail.

4) *Zero-g*. Lack of gravity has not been a major problem for the rubidium and cesium clocks now used in space. For cesium fountains and hydrogen masers it is.

5) *Vacuum/thermal*. Almost every clock technology is affected by the absence of air. The primary effect is thermal. The good aspect is that it's easier to insulate things when there's no air. That same aspect turns out to be a significant problem when it comes to considering cooling circuitry.

6) *Radiation*. This environment is unique to space. Depending on the orbit, a space clock may see as much as 100,000 rads over its life, as well as upsets in the electronics resulting from particles that are not seen on the surface of the earth. Radiation hard circuit topologies have been developed with specialized components and circuitry. However, finding suitable parts to implement them for a clock can be difficult.

7) *Reliability*. Continuous un-interrupted performance must be designed into the clock from the initial design. It is more than having the right parts. The designer must make sure that the stress on the parts has sufficient margin within the potential thermal limits, projected radiation effects, circuit design and parts quality. These factors all interact to produce predictable performance over the projected life of the clock.

8) *Quality*. This factor involves the process used to build the clock. The process used to build the clock can be a critical factor in performance and operating life. The conventional definition of quality is that all the clocks in a production run are identically built to the same standards with the same procedures and parts of traceable pedigree. Logically they should then operate almost identically, but as demonstrated in GPS operations, identical clocks can have quite different performance characteristics.

9) *Operability*. Finally, as a clock is designed to run in its space environment the ability to control or monitor its performance, either automatically or from the ground must be decided. The designer has to decide which functions should be remotely controllable and the key monitors to indicate performance and give an indication of potential problems or failure. If a processor is used in the clock, it's also necessary to decide to what extent it should be re-programmable on-orbit. Early in the development process these capabilities are maximized, but the final results are to

minimize risk of failure due to additional complexity, determine the clock's interaction within operation with other elements of the system, and determine the minimum telemetry and monitoring necessary. The amount of information necessary in the up and down links to the satellites can have a significant overall system impact.

III. CASE STUDIES

A. Space Hydrogen Maser

In the 1980's as the GPS system was being developed for deployment, a clock development program was initiated to address on-orbit clock operational problems with the Block I spacecraft and extend the commercial availability and performance of space clocks for the GPS program [3]. One aspect of that program was to develop a space qualified hydrogen maser to provide increased long-term performance over the existing cesium and rubidium clocks [4]. The maser program is a good example of how the special needs of space clocks can impact design.

The state of the art maser in the late 1970's was the VLG-11 made by the Smithsonian Astrophysical Observatory (Fig. 1) [5]. These masers were hand built in limited production principally for Very Long Baseline Interferometry. The Allan Deviation at around 1000 seconds was better than 1×10^{-15} . The first major design challenges were the size, weight, and power. A VLG-11 weighs around 400 pounds, is mounted in 4-foot tall specially constructed cabinet, and had a steady state power consumption of about 150 watts. This size and power consumption would be acceptable for a free flying satellite. Efforts into re-design for a satellite version were initially based on the experimental unit used in Gravity Probe A (Fig. 2) [6] designed to operate over an approximately 2 hour ballistic flight ending up in the Atlantic Ocean. Exploratory units built in the late 1970's for NRL by Hughes Research Laboratories (HRL) [7] and the

Figure 1, SAO VLG-11 Hydrogen Maser

RCA Sarnoff Research Center [8] were of this large active maser design. The goals for a satellite version were about 30 inches in length, 50 pounds weight, and 50 watts of power.

Figure 2. Gravity Probe A Hydrogen Maser

An active hydrogen maser's dimensions are determined primarily by the 1.4 GHz tuned microwave cavity needed to obtain the high Q necessary for maser oscillation. The work by Vessot had shown it was possible to reduce the outer dimensions of the maser and get the weight down to about 90 pounds in the Gravity Probe A configuration. The active maser work done at HRL, Sarnoff Labs and NRL had shown that another factor of two size reduction was obviously going to be very difficult without changing the design approach.

A method of reducing the size of a microwave cavity was loading with a dielectric material. Easton, at NRL, designed a cavity about 6 to 7 inches long with a diameter of about 4 inches that was dielectrically loaded by a single crystal sapphire cylinder (Fig. 4). This smaller cavity [9] would

Figure 3. Hughes Research Lab Exploratory Development Space Active Maser Unit with Laboratory Electronics

Figure 4. Dielectrically Loaded Passive Maser Cavity shown disassembled with Single Crystal Sapphire Cylinder

Figure 5. HRL Compact Space Maser Magnatron Cavity

appeared to make the 50 pound goal attainable, but it came at the cost of reducing the cavity Q by a factor of 4 to around 7000, well below the threshold of oscillation. Another approach to a smaller cavity by Wang at Hughes Research Laboratories (HRL) (Fig. 5) was by using a magnetron cavity design [10]. This design also reduces the cavity Q below that required for active oscillation.

To operate with smaller low Q cavities the approach was to use the electronics in a different mode of operation. This then resulted in a major change to the electronics for a satellite version maser. Two electronics approaches were investigated. Walls at NIST demonstrated a passive design hydrogen maser that could operate interrogating a low Q hydrogen maser cavity in a manner similar to cesium or rubidium designs (Fig. 6) [8]. Wang at Hughes Research Laboratory took a different approach and used Q-multiplication [7] to raise the effective Q of the loaded cavity high enough to support oscillation (Fig. 7). Both designs shared another problem in that pulling of the hydrogen line resonance resulted from cavity mistuning. This problem was not new to hydrogen masers but was particularly strong in the small cavity designs. Cavity pulling introduced a frequency drift in the clocks that would negate much of the stability advantage of a maser. Both designs addressed the

Figure 6. NIST Passive Maser Electronics Block Diagram

Figure 7. HRL Q-Enhanced Electronics Block Diagram

problem by adding a second servo to center the cavity resonance on the hydrogen line.

In these different cavity approaches a major consideration was the mechanical design that would be capable of surviving the launch environment. Neither cavity design was originally intended to withstand the rigors of launch. The primary problem was the cavity mounting since the NIST and NRL cavities contained a solid dielectric cylinder of cervit and sapphire respectively, having a mass of several kilograms. The Hughes design was much lighter but used a quartz bulb with glued-on electrodes. Vessot was able to design a mechanical package for the NRL sapphire cavity using titanium and a spring washer to support the cavity [11]. Hughes solved the electrode problem by applying the electrodes as a coating to the maser bulb [12].

Advanced development models using the NRL and NIST cavity designs are shown in Fig. 8. Several of the NRL cavity designs were built to incorporate and investigate other elements of maser design, such as the hydrogen supply system including dissociator, hexa- and quadra-pole magnetic state selectors, hydrogen getters to remove the excess hydrogen from the system, shielding effectiveness and other electronic issues. The results of these tests, experiments and other developments were coordinated with

the Hughes Division were under contract for either the spacecraft, ground or supporting efforts by HRL [11].

Figure 8. NRL Passive Space Maser Advanced Development Model (Left) and NIST Passive Maser (Right)

Space does have one advantage in the case of the maser and that is the vacuum significantly helps thermal insulation. Without the conductive losses of air in the insulation around the physics package, it was possible to use specially designed insulation to significantly reduce power consumption. However, in the case of the dielectric cavity units the mass of the cavity and the overall unit gave way to the lighter HRL cavity with development of solutions to the mounting, launch and thermal environment problems. The mass reduction and power reduction more than compensated for the increased complexity of the Q-enhanced electronic design. The protoflight Compact Hydrogen Maser produced by Hughes Space and Communication Division is shown in Fig. 9. This unit was designed to interface on-board a Block II/IIA operational spacecraft for potential flight verification [13,14]. The stability of the prototype unit and that of a

Figure 9. Hughes Space & Comm Division Protoflight Space Compact Hydrogen Maser with Electronics Package

subcompact maser model built at HRL (Fig. 10) are shown in comparison with a VLG-11 maser in Fig. 11.

Figure 10. HRL Subcompact Space Hydrogen Maser without Electronics

Figure 11. Space Hydrogen Maser and VLG-11 Stability Performance

B. Current Developments

Datum Corporation is developing an optically pumped cesium clock for potential space use for GPS [15]. The design has legacy to their digital space cesium clock to be used in GPS Block IIF and also to their experimental laboratory version optically pumped cesium clock. Since this new space design builds on earlier space cesium designs, many of the major design issues have already been addressed. However, the addition of new technology, and in

this case a single mode-locked laser system for optical pumping, many of the design issues for space are re-opened.

The mechanical design of a space clock using precisely aligned optical components has unique problems to be solved. Laboratory clocks are typically built on optical tables and commercial units for ground use are yet to be available. An optical table allows precise alignments and reduction of vibration effects, however its usual size of several square meters of area and mass of hundreds of kilograms preclude routine use in unmanned spacecraft. Consequently, the necessary reduction or substitution of an optical alignment device or structure is a challenge to the development of possible new type of space atomic clock. Coupled with the other factors such as temperature the end result could well result in a unique design and unit.

IV. SUMMARY

The space qualification factors and the resulting development requirements that necessitated complete re-design and development of hydrogen masers for space is briefly summarized in Table 1. These factors resulted in the design, qualification and evaluation of units being considerably different than earth bound units.

TABLE 1
DESIGN IMPACTS OF SPACE FOR THE MASER

Parameter	Change	Impact
Weight, size, & power	90% reduction in size and a factor of four in power	Cavity design and operating mode
Mechanical	Shock @ 2000 G's Acceleration @ 20 G Random Vibration @ 9 G rms	New cavity, mounting, materials, titanium structure
Vacuum/thermal	Increased thermal control over 0° to 100° C Range	New cavity insulation, new electronics design, new dissociator
Radiation	Natural and Enhanced Environment	Electronics design and materials selection
Reliability	Design life of 7.5 years	Vacuum system and electronics
Quality	Producible design	New procedures, parts, testing and materials
Operability	Remote operation	Controls, telemetry electronics and vehicle interface

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